

Beijing's Cyber Identity Card Scheme: A Dual Threat to the Chinese Government and Civil Society

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Abstract

This paper examines the potential risks and challenges posed by the proposed cyber identity card (CIC) scheme in China. It argues that this initiative presents a dual threat to both the Chinese government and citizens in terms of data security, privacy protection, and social stability. The centralized management of citizens' data online raises concerns about the vulnerability to cyber-attacks and the erosion of individual privacy rights. The paper also highlights the risks of further restricting citizens' freedom of expression and the potential for social unrest. It concludes by calling for a more open and democratic approach that allows for diverse voices and seeks a win-win solution for both the government and citizens.

Keywords: *online privacy, cybersecurity, individual privacy, privacy protection, social development.*

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The Rationale and Background of the Present Study

On the evening of July 26, 2024, Xinhua News Agency (<https://www.xinhuanet.com/>) published a report on its website titled "Soliciting Public Opinions on the Administrative Measures for National Cyber Identity Authentication Public Service". The article emphasized that "in order to strengthen the protection of citizens' personal information, promote and standardize the construction and application of national cyber identity authentication public services, and accelerate the implementation of the trusted cyber identity strategy, the Ministry of Public Security and the Cyberspace Administration of China have drafted the 'Administrative Measures for National Cyber Identity Authentication Public Service (Draft for Comments)' based on relevant laws and regulations, and are soliciting public opinions starting from July 26" (Xiong & Wang, 2024). Subsequently, major media outlets such as People's Daily Online (<https://www.people.com.cn>), The Paper (<https://www.thepaper.cn/>), and Qilu Net (<https://www.iqilu.com/>) released the news, formally launching the "cyber identity card" scheme that has sparked heated discussions among Chinese citizens.

This can be seen as the Chinese government poised to restrict the civil right to cyber freedom in the name of "national cybersecurity," as well as to interfere with citizens' privacy using political and administrative measures. A tangentially related incidence occurred in April of the same year when the

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Ministry of State Security announced the "Procedural Provisions on Administrative Law Enforcement by State Security" and "Procedural Provisions on Handling Criminal Cases by State Security" (which officially came into effect on July 1 of the same year). Notably, this administrative document consists of 7 chapters and 140 articles, including general provisions, preventive guidance, investigation and evidence collection, requisition and compensation, administrative penalties, time limits and service, and supplementary provisions. It explicitly states that civil organizations, including civil groups, are required to "accept the coordination, guidance, supervision and inspection of State Security in accordance with the law." In particular, the directive allows state security to conduct on-site inspections of "relevant individuals' and groups' electronic devices, facilities, and related procedures and tools," raising concerns about whether this means state security will arbitrarily inspect the mobile phones of citizens entering and leaving the country (Cao, 2024). To date, this question remains unanswered by credible sources.

Therefore, in view of homogeneity in both the content and release time of these two documents, it may be reasonable to consider whether the government's call for "cyber identity cards" is a move towards further tightening the restrictions on citizens' rights to cyber freedom. Correspondingly, once the Cyber Identity Card scheme is finally up and running, will citizens likely lose more options for personal privacy protection? At the same time, it is important to note that due to the homogeneity of China's current political system and the centralization of political discourse power, any release of the draft for public comments likely means the final outcome has already been predetermined by those in control of the relevant political discourse before its release. From this perspective, if it is indeed not the government's intention to see how far they can go with public opinion, then the Cyber Identity Card scheme will very much likely be implemented. This move may lead to further government curtailment on the options available for citizens to protect their privacy. In today's society where reality and virtuality are highly interconnected, internet monitoring and control will greatly contribute to the trajectory of citizens becoming "naked in Cyberspace".

In this context, cybersecurity may be more than an important strategic issue for the government; more significantly it may be an essential component of national security. From this perspective, maintaining national cybersecurity is not only the government's responsibility but also its legal obligation to protect citizens from cyber threats. However, this raises a problem: to a large extent it violates the original intent of maintaining cybersecurity if the government excessively monitors and controls citizens' rights to personal privacy in the name of maintaining cybersecurity, although maintaining cybersecurity as a government responsibility and obligation may be necessary for the government. However, the Chinese government seems to have enacted policies against citizens' autonomy by excessively monitoring and controlling them. Indeed, the relevant laws, regulations, and policy documents implemented by the Chinese government are in a game of tug-of-war with citizens' personal privacy rights. From the perspective of information symmetry, this situation is like having a "game of incomplete information" as in game theory (Harsanyi, 1995).

In addition, the centralized database management model to be utilized for the Cyber Identity Card scheme will also become a major threat to the country's long-term stability and peace (Kelly, 2012). The centralized management model may make an ideal target for cyber hackers (Samtani, Chinn, Chen & Nunamaker Jr, 2017). Given the successive releases of the aforementioned government directives, the government seems to be intentionally synchronizing centralized data management and public surveillance. If the former risk poses a threat to the country's cybersecurity and government stability, then the latter may be a devastating blow to the protection of personal privacy once citizens' personal details are collected and retained centrally by government procedures. Citizens will largely lose their rights to privacy, which will threaten the future democratic development of Chinese society.

Risks of Centralized Data Management

In terms of centralized data management, existing research has focused more on discussing the risks of centralized data management in economic studies, with little coverage of the public data security risks

mentioned in this paper. The current practices of both centralized data management and government-controlled data custody carry significant risks, which will be discussed separately below.

First, in terms of the risks of centralized data management, a huge, unified body of databases will be established to operationalize the Cyber Identity Card scheme. This means central online management of citizens' identity information and online footprints. While this centralized data management model can to some extent enhance the government's capacity to combat cybercrime, it also comes with critical vulnerabilities. Meanwhile, it is important to note that from a perspective of strategic intelligence analysis, this type of centralized data management system may be detrimental to the country's future cybersecurity as it is very likely to become a key target for cyber hackers. With China's population of over one billion, any single data leak could have far-reaching consequences, potentially affecting the personal privacy of tens of millions of citizens, if hackers successfully attack the data management system. If this strand of data is also linked to citizens' financial assets or internal government data, the loss would be even more disastrous. Furthermore, significant changes in the workflows of the centralized data management model, coupled with the inability to promptly introduce and update corresponding process control measures, may give rise to blind spots in institutional management. This, in turn, may increase the risk of lagging institutional management (Zhang, 2019). Therefore, centralized data management may be highly risky for both the government and the public.

In terms of government-controlled data custody, the centralized control of data custodianships may further intensify the government's expanding authority over the public. In the short term, this approach may seem effective for the government to exercise power over the public. However, over time, centralized control and management may backfire and lead to reversed outcomes as dissent builds up as citizens become disadvantaged from the perspective of social development, thus affecting the government's long-term interests. For the public, once sentiments reach a tipping point, extreme revolutionary possibilities may arise. As Eric Hoffer mentioned in his book, *The True Believer*, many people join revolutionary movements because they long for revolution to rapidly and dramatically change their living conditions (Eric, 2019, P25). As the effects of reaching a critical juncture accumulate, the tipping point arrives when the entity subject to supervisory control launches an attack against the very governing body exerting said control. This confrontation between the two opposing forces ultimately risks rupturing the delicate balance between the government and the populace. In fact, within the contemporary Chinese social system, the equilibrium between the state and its citizens has arguably already shown signs of disequilibrium. The Cyber Identity Card policy will further increase the risk of social rifts.

Risks of Reduced Public Free Space

The Cyber Identity Card has also raised concerns about the shrinking of public free space in Chinese society. This troubling trend, far from improving, has only intensified in recent years. The emergence of the Cyber Identity Card stands as a stark symbol of the gradual erosion of public freedoms.

The Chinese government's tightening control over public discourse is a primary concern regarding the shrinking of public free space. The government increasingly silences online voices that diverge from its ruling ideology. Regarding the Cyber Identity Card scheme, a university professor who expressed dissenting views had his content deleted and Weibo account censored, exemplifying a common occurrence in China's internet society (Guo, 2015; Fang, 2024; Ma, 2021; Cao, 2015). Facing restrictions, deletions, silencing, and bans has become a marker of speaking out against the government.

Even more alarming is the trend towards allowing only one voice to dominate - the mainstream ideas aligning with the central government's will. As Hannah Arendt describes in *The Origins of Totalitarianism*, when a totalitarian movement establishes the "will of the Leader" as the supreme law, individual capabilities lose significance (Hannah, 2014, P478). The Chinese government's control over public opinion appears to be realizing Arendt's caveat, fostering a climate of "organized and terrifying public opinion" where dissent is not tolerated and reality depends on the existence of a "non-totalitarian

world" (Hannah, 2014, P493). This alarming trend extends beyond devouring public discourse to actively promoting a singular, "correct" consciousness aligned with leadership.

The shrinking space for public opinion also jeopardizes individual autonomy. Citizens may feel compelled to reduce their participation in political activities and public discussions. Moreover, the requirement for real-name authentication undermines anonymity, which is crucial for free speech. In China's sensitive political climate, the absence of anonymity further erodes freedom of expression.

Without anonymity, citizens may self-censor and refrain from criticizing the government or policies, fearing retaliation or social exclusion (Nughat, 2021). Prolonged self-suppression can fuel societal opposition and retaliation. The loss of anonymity stifles diverse opinions and weakens critical and innovative thinking. Aware of surveillance, citizens may curtail criticism and unconsciously engage in self-censorship (Adamska, 2017). This suppresses individual expression and diminishes the diversity of public discourse, hindering societal openness and progress.

Furthermore, this trend may weaken civil society, reducing public participation and impeding democratization and government transparency. While the Cyber Identity Card may temporarily enhance government control, it risks severe consequences and potential net losses. For the restricted populace, it may be oppressive and even sow the seeds of revolutionary sentiment.

Risks of Lack of Privacy Protection Mechanisms

In the current social climate, rights to privacy are becoming increasingly ambiguous. From a strategic perspective, this ambiguity appears to be setting the stage for more intrusive monitoring and control in the future.

The public information released about the Cyber Identity Card scheme lacks a demarcation of legal provisions and administrative responsibilities. Legislation often lags behind social needs, contrary to the timeliness pursued by journalists (Xiong, Yu, Zhang & Leng, 2021). Puzzlingly, in modern China, both legislation and journalism seem to be experiencing delays in addressing social issues. As a result, the legal and data security risks associated with the Cyber Identity Card scheme may become even more critical.

Without clear legal support, the risk of data leaks and abuse is significantly heightened. The government and interested parties may exploit this data for unrestricted surveillance and even predict personal behavior, threatening individual privacy and autonomy. Moreover, data misuse can harm not only information privacy but also restrict personal freedom, such as through a "social credit system" that influences credit ratings and social status. These are all critical risk factors to consider. In addition, there is another obvious threat factor, which is the multiple identities that the government possesses in this situation. This is also an important reason why the author added the word "mechanism" in the title of this section. This is not the behavior of individuals or isolated cases, nor the performance of collectives or communities, but the loss of control of an overall mechanism. In this situation, the advocates, formulators, revisers, and decision-makers of the regulations, as well as the managers of data, supervisors of behavior, maintainers of legislation, users of data, internal and external supervisors, and protectors of public sentiment and opinion, all fall into the hands of the government, this huge collective controlling machine. This is a loophole in the entire Chinese political and government mechanism and a strong hidden danger for triggering future social crises. It is also a mechanism risk that the entire political operation system and government management system must face. Once a loss of control effect is triggered, the entire social mechanism in China may face the risk of collapse at that time.

The risks to individual privacy protection directly impact the public, but in terms of overall development and systemic connections, they are intertwined with state authority. While state may relish the centralized power granted by the Cyber Identity Card scheme, this undemocratic measure is unsustainable in the long run. Addressing the issue early on is safer and less costly than attempting to rectify it later when it has become entrenched. Although retracting the Cyber Identity Card scheme may appear to loosen the government's grip on the public, it is ultimately more advantageous for the government. By doing so, the

government could even enhance its public reputation. Given the potential benefits, this approach seems advisable.

Conclusion

The question of whether to pursue a mutually beneficial outcome or descend into shared harm is a conundrum that the Chinese government must grapple with and a matter that every Chinese citizen must contemplate deeply. Embracing diversity, maintaining openness, and allowing dissenting voices to exist are not only crucial indicators of whether the ruling government is open to democratic practices but also important benchmarks for gauging the populace's own pursuit of democracy and the degree of open-mindedness in their thinking. The Cyber Identity Card scheme, currently a topic of fervent discussion in Chinese society, represents a costly test for the Chinese government and a profound challenge for the Chinese people themselves. To attain the desired rights and to live in the envisioned social environment, this collective must first stand up, voice their aspirations, demonstrate their stance, and seek a win-win scenario rather than a path of mutual harm.

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